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Abstract:

Based on the communities identified the SSHOC project, this is the first of two deliverables that will indicate the actions taken to engage the stakeholders, and the effectiveness of the communication and promotional campaigns. Two iterations foreseen.

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Executive Summary

SSHOC is a 40-month project which unites 23 partner organisations¹ and their 25 associates in developing the social sciences and humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)². After 2 years point, this report examines project activities from the perspective of stakeholder engagement, evaluates their impact in terms of progress against defined targets, and lays out the plan to increase uptake of key project results over the final months.

The report opens with an analysis of the eight categories of stakeholders identified by project partners as most likely to benefit from seamless access to high quality SSH research data, and the tools and resources to facilitate data processing and analysis. These stakeholders include individual researchers and research networks, research and e-infrastructures, research libraries and funders, universities, policymakers and citizen scientists. Across the board and whether to a greater or a lesser extent, each group is a potential end user of one or more of the assets around which the engagement strategy articulates.

Assets brought to the consortium by SSHOC partners or to be developed within the project are then listed and described. These assets include a comprehensive suite of research data management tools and services, and a training programme. A further asset which is being developed from scratch by project partners is the SSH Open Marketplace. A discovery portal designed to facilitate access to the tools, software, datasets, and training materials produced within the project and also to external resources which together furnish the complete data management requirements across the research life cycle.

The bulk of the report is dedicated to describing the stakeholder engagement strategy follow-up and implementation, which is elaborated along the following major lines: events, and aggregating researchers into smaller communities via a series of calls, interviews, surveys and publications, activating communities and publications. These activities are supported by the SSHOC website and social media channels.

An analysis of engagement activities by stakeholder group over the first 24 months of the project shows that a solid network has been established with researchers, universities, libraries, and EOSC initiatives, and many of the associated key performance targets achieved. These efforts will be intensified during the remaining 16 months alongside increased engagement with research funding institutions, the private sector and industry, policymakers, and citizens and citizen scientists.

¹ SSHOC partners page on the website: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/partners> [accessed 16.03.2021]

² EOSC Portal website: <http://www.eosc-portal.eu> [accessed 16.03.2021]

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESS	European Social Survey
EVS	European Values Study
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
GGP	Generations and Gender Programme
OSPP	Open Science Policy Platform
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

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1. Introduction

SSHOC project partners identified relevant stakeholder groups during the proposal stage, so that engagement could begin as soon as possible. These groups were aligned with those identified by the EOSC pilot project³, the recommendations of the Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP)⁴, and insights from SSHOC partners as to the user communities most likely to benefit from project outputs.

Eight stakeholder categories for SSHOC are identified in D2.1 *SSHOC Overall Communication and Outreach Plan*⁵ and D6.1 *SSHOC Community Engagement Strategy*⁶. Of these, the primary stakeholders are researchers and research & e-infrastructures, EOSC thematic clusters, followed by universities and research libraries.

FIGURE 1: SSHOC STAKEHOLDERS

This report examines completed and planned project activities from the perspective of each stakeholder and evaluates the impact of those completed at the time of writing.

Overall, the project can be said to have made positive progress, in terms of engaging influential champions and setting up communities of users which in some cases have already begun to experiment with our project

³ EOSC Pilot website: <https://eoscpilot.eu/> [accessed 15.03.2021]

⁴ Open Science Policy Platform Recommendations:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/integrated_advice_opsp_recommendations.pdf [accessed 15.03.2021]

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595935> [accessed 15.03.2021]

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592244> [accessed 15.03.2021]

assets and outputs. Examples of these SSHOC champions and communities are tabulated below by stakeholder category.

TABLE 1: SAMPLE OF END-USER CHAMPIONS AND COMMUNITIES BY STAKEHOLDER CATEGORIES

End-user category	Champion or community	Context
Researchers	<p>Agnieszka Szulińska (The Digital Humanities Centre at the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences)</p> <p>Vanessa Hanneschläger (Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage)</p> <p>Maurizio Toscano (University of Granada)</p> <p>Kasia Karpinska (ODISSEI)</p>	<p>Selected applicants to call for testers of the SSH Open Marketplace, live at the ICTeSSH 2020 workshop <i>"Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: User Workshop"</i></p>
EOSC, thematic clusters and e-Research Infrastructures	<p>EOSC-Life</p> <p>ENVRI-FAIR</p> <p>ESCAPE</p> <p>PaNOSC</p>	<p>Several joint communication activities and joint sessions, highlighting the bundled <i>"Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC"</i> and the <i>"Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud"</i> at the <i>Realising EOSC conference</i>", November 2020</p>
Policymakers	<p>Liina Munari, Deputy Head of Unit C1 "eInfrastructure and Science Cloud", DG CONNECT</p> <p>Cristian Cuciniello, Policy Assistant at European Commission</p>	<p>Munari was the invited keynote speaker at the <i>Realising EOSC conference</i>, November 2020</p> <p>Cuciniello took part in the discussion and provided recommendations taken up in the report on <i>"EOSC. ESFRI Cluster Projects. RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services"</i>, at RDA Plenary 14, Helsinki, October 2019</p>
Research Libraries and Archives	<p>14 SSH repositories selected to receive SSHOC support for CoreTrustSeal certification</p> <p>LIBER (Association for European</p>	<p>Call for repositories June - September 2020</p> <p>Workshops at LIBER 2019 and 2020 conferences</p>

End-user category	Champion or community	Context
	Research Libraries) Working Groups on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen science, • Digital humanities and cultural heritage, • Digital skills for library staff and researchers. 	SSH Training Community
Research Performing Organisations and Universities	European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST)	SSHOC training session during the COST Action meeting and 2nd Annual Policy Dialogue Conference, Brussels, Belgium SSHOC presentation at the COST Action CA16111 (ETHMIGSURVEYDATA) meeting, Rome, Italy
Citizen Scientists and Civil Society	Europeana LIBER Citizen Science Working Group The Bentham Project Transcribathon	The session " <i>Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?</i> " at the Realising EOSC conference, November 2020 explored the potential for citizens and citizen scientists to participate in scientific progress via open SSH data. The session was co-organised with the LIBER Citizen Science Working Group
Private Sector and Industry	EOSC Digital Innovation Hub EUHubs4Data	Joint session at the Realising EOSC conference, " <i>Engaging the Private Sector. About roadblocks and success stories in the uptake of EOSC services</i> ".
Research Funding Organisations	DG CNECT & RTD	DG CNECT & RTD meeting "Building EOSC through H2020 projects" in September 2019

2. Stakeholders & End Users

The table below outlines the potential benefits offered by SSHOC to each of the stakeholder groups identified. Clearly, while the extent varies from group to group, there are potential direct end-users of SSHOC outputs in each group.

TABLE 2: ADDED VALUE FOR SSHOC TARGETED END-USER COMMUNITIES

Stakeholder	Potential Benefits to be Derived from SSHOC
Researchers (Research networks and associations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seamless access to high quality research data ● Easy access to tools and resources to facilitate data processing and analysis ● Access to secure and trusted repositories for storing data ● Access to tutorials, training materials, user stories ● A self-assessment feature to rate their contribution to research in the humanities
Research & e-Infrastructures (EOSC Thematic Clusters)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A common governance model for the treatment of thematic data ● Common policies on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FAIR ○ data stewardship and harmonisation ○ quality assessment and impact ● Context-driven training ● Increased opportunities to attract users to e-infrastructures ● Increased opportunities to gain visibility and recognition through representation in the EOSC ● Support in CoreTrustSeal certification for repositories
Research Libraries & Archives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seamless access to data with which to enrich existing data collections ● Enhanced support of research activities through easy access to tools and services with which to boost the visibility and value of data offered to scientific and policy communities ● Access to tutorials, training materials, user stories
Universities & Research Performing Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Facilitated exchange of research data between individual institutions, driving improved research robustness and verification, and accelerating the rate of scientific discovery ● Seamless access to data with which to enrich existing data collections ● Easy access to tools and services with which to boost the visibility and value of data offered to students, academic staff and the scientific community as a whole

Stakeholder	Potential Benefits to be Derived from SSHOC
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access to secure and trusted repositories for storing data ● Access to tutorials and training materials ● Access to trained data stewardship professionals with domain-specific skills
Policy Making Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access to national and institutional data scalable at a European level ● Easier management of IPRs and ethical issues as a result of harmonised data policies ● Access to reports on legislative or interoperability issues affecting data handling across geographical and disciplinary borders
Research Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access to national and institutional data scalable at a European level ● Easier management of IPRs and ethical issues as a result of harmonised data policies
Private Sector & Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access to promotional and new business opportunities via the SSH Open Marketplace ● A means of interacting with researchers to improve service quality
Civil Society and Citizen Scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Opportunities to participate in scientific progress via open access to SSH data, services and tools.

3. Engaging User Communities: Key Exploitable Results

Promoting the use of Key Exploitable Results, named assets from here on, brought to the consortium by SSHOC partners or developed within the project has been a key means of engaging with user communities. These assets are briefly described in the following section and include:

- Tools and services - such as the SSHOC vocabulary initiative, the citation module, the switchboard, and the machine translation evaluation kit
- Training - both the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit and the SSH Training Community itself
- The SSH Open Marketplace.

3.1 SSHOC Tools and Services

Between January 2019 and April 2022 SSHOC will deliver a series of services and tools for daily use by SSH researchers. The timeline below indicates their earliest availability.

FIGURE 2: TIMELINE: SSHOC SERVICES AND TOOLS

These SSHOC-developed, co-developed and enhanced services and tools will be made available through the SSH Open Marketplace by December 2021. In the meantime, they are being incorporated into a searchable catalogue on the SSHOC website as they come on stream and promoted individually to the appropriate end-user communities.

3.2 SSH Open Marketplace

The SSH Open Marketplace is a discovery portal designed to offer social sciences and humanities researchers the tools, software, datasets, training materials, and workflows they need to manage their data across the full research life cycle.

FIGURE 3: SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE BETA RELEASE JANUARY 2021

FIGURE 4: SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE TIMELINE

In January 2021, boasting some 5000 individual records - and just released to the public in a Beta version, the SSH Open Marketplace offers a powerful opportunity to create user engagement. (Refer to Section 4.3.1 of this document on SSH Open Marketplace Tester Community). The resource will continue to evolve throughout 2021 with delivery of the final product scheduled for December 2021.

3.3 SSH Training

Training activities within SSHOC are led by expert trainers, cherry picked from recognised partner organisations. In addition to an ongoing programme of training workshops and webinars focused on topics of fundamental importance and interest to the SSH Community as a whole, the team offers **Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps** to enable trainers to develop and improve both their professional skills and their knowledge of the SSH research data landscape. The Train-the-Trainer approach is used in order to create and empower multipliers.

FIGURE 5: POSTER EXCERPT: SSH TRAINING DISCOVERY TOOLKIT

The Training Discovery Toolkit is a work in progress and currently offers more than 70 separate items from 40 recognised sources on a multitude of topics.

Resource Types

- Educational materials for trainers on didactics
- Games to stimulate interaction during training sessions
- Multimedia resources to teach researchers about Open Science

How you use it

STEP 1: Type in your search topic (e.g., GDPR)

STEP 2: Refine your search (Filter by: Entity type, Collections, Intended audience, Language, Source of item, Curated topic, Discipline, Format)

STEP 3: Select the item (e.g., GDPR in Research: Practical guidance, examples and question/answers for researchers on how to apply the General Data Protection Regulation in research where personal data are collected / processed. Language: English, License: CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, Intended audience: Researcher, Student, Disciplines: Social Sciences, Curated topics: Research data management/FAIR data, Last updated: 2019-12-01, Access point: https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/datacatalog/legal-ethics/gdpr-in-research.aspx, Source of item: UK Data Service: Manage Data)

STEP 4: Access your Resource (e.g., Applying GDPR in research)

Another feature of training in SSHOC is the **SSH Training Discovery Toolkit**, an inventory of learning materials. This resource is in constant evolution as feedback is continuously received from the **SSH Training Community**. At the time of writing, this members-only group numbers some **150 professional trainers worldwide**. Monthly meetings are arranged for this group, to discuss topics suggested by members.

4. Engaging User Communities: Key Mechanisms

As defined in SSHOC Overall Communication and Outreach Plan (D2.1) and SSHOC Community Engagement Strategy (D6.1), the SSHOC consortium engages with stakeholders primarily through:

- Events,
- Calls, interviews, and surveys,
- Creating communities,
- Online presence,
- Publications, scientific and other.

A further mechanism is collaborating with other EOSC cluster projects and relevant projects and initiatives, discussed in chapter 5.

4.1 Events

Events include training initiatives organised by SSHOC such as workshops, webinars, Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps and SSH training community calls. Events also include workshops and webinars aimed at raising awareness of SSHOC amongst targeted stakeholder groups. The final conference is an example. Finally, events include SSHOC visibility at third party events.

For the purpose of this analysis, we distinguish between events organised by SSHOC and events organised by other parties.

4.1.1 SSHOC organised Workshops and Webinars

During the period of January 2019 to December 2020 (first official EC reporting period), the SSHOC consortium organised 4 consortium meetings, inviting and engaging with the EOSC cluster projects and wider EOSC initiatives. In addition, the consortium organised and co-hosted **38 end-user focused workshops and webinars, actively engaging over 2580 participants from the full scope of stakeholder categories**, as listed in the tables of Annex 1.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic that affected the organisation of face-to-face events in the second year of the project, 27 events were organised in a digital format. Recordings were published and shared with the SSHOC community for reuse. As of February 2021, the published **recordings of these engagement events had been viewed over 2640 times in total**.

FIGURE 6: #REALISINGEOSC VIRTUAL CONFERENCE HALL

One such event was **Realising the European Open Science Cloud**, part of the stakeholder series, the virtual conference organised as a collaboration between SSHOC, EOSC-hub and FREYA in November 2020. The conference was subtitled **“Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences, humanities and beyond”** and invited participants to join forces and connect with e-infrastructures, discover new tools and techniques and aggregate services to the EOSC Portal. The organisers made every effort to create an original and engaging experience for some **690 conference attendees** from **45 countries**.

Aside from more than 30 plenary and small group breakout sessions over the four days, the conference offered virtual exhibition booths and a networking area, project chat rooms, a scavenger hunt with clues, and contests with prizes for booth holders and participants. An online conference report is available, presenting an overview of the event with links to supporting information about each session and the associated video recording⁷.

⁷ Realising EOSC conference announcement <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/realising-eosc-virtual-conference-difference> [accessed 15.03.2021]

FIGURE 7: ATTENDANCE AT EVENTS BY STAKEHOLDER TYPE

The graphic above summarizes stakeholder attendance at all SSHOC organised events to date and confirms researchers, EOSC and research e-Infrastructures, research performing organisations and research libraries and archives as the key groups. Representatives from policymaking and research funding organisations received special invitations.

4.1.2 SSHOC Visibility at Third-party Events

There was a SSHOC presence at **66 third-party events in the first two years, representing 77 presentations, posters and appearances in panel discussions. (Refer Annex 2.)**

Participant numbers varied from five at invitation-only discussion meetings with EC policymakers, to more than 500 at large, researcher-targeted conferences.

FIGURE 8: THE NUMBER OF THIRD-PARTY EVENTS TARGETED BY STAKEHOLDER TYPE

The graphic above indicates the stakeholder groups targeted at the third-party events where SSHOC had visibility. For example, of the total of 66 events attended, researchers were the key target at 48 events. The graphic shows that events with a clear focus on research libraries and archives, research e-Infrastructures and EOSC, research performing organisations, and researchers were selected.

4.2 Calls, Surveys, and Interviews

To align SSHOC work with the needs of researchers, and to involve researchers in development activities, specific calls were issued in different project areas.

4.2.1 Call for SSH Open Marketplace Testers

In April 2020, SSHOC looked for SSH researchers willing to test the Alpha release of the SSH Open Marketplace and report back on their experience at a dedicated user workshop *Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace* held during the **ICTeSSH 2020**⁸ virtual conference.

The call was widely disseminated through SSHOC channels and the consortium networks and resulted in the selection of four testers from different SSH domains, European countries and career stages. Each tester was granted privileged access to the SSH Open Marketplace a week prior to the workshop and asked to test the

⁸ Agile development SSH Open Marketplace User Workshop announcement <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/agile-development-ssh-open-marketplace-user-workshop> [accessed 15.03.2021]

platform and services on the basis of a set of predefined questions. In a roundtable discussion during the workshop, the testers were called on individually to share their findings and comments with the other attendees.

After the event, further testers were recruited to provide additional feedback which fed into the Beta release of the SSH Open Marketplace in January 2021.

FIGURE 9: NEWS ITEM PROMOTING ICTESSH2020 HANDS-ON SESSION

4.2.2 Call for SSH Repository Certification Support

The D8.2 *Certification plan for SSHOC repositories*⁹ report of February 2020 lays the groundwork for the adoption of Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) standards and the FAIR principles in data repositories across the social sciences and humanities. The report charts the current trust landscape within the SSHOC communities, explains CoreTrustSeal in detail, and identifies the repositories which will be the main focus of support activities during the course of the project. The report also describes the modes of support to be employed within the SSHOC project to assist repositories in reaching TDR certification.

⁹ D8.2 Certification Plan SSHOC repositories <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/d82-certification-plan-sshoc-repositories> [accessed 15.03.2021]

After publishing the above-mentioned report, **SSHOC invited applications from SSH repositories interested in receiving support in achieving CoreTrustSeal certification.** Successful applicants would qualify for one or more of the following modes of support:

1. The provision of preliminary information about available resources
2. Interactive tutorials
3. Feedback on self-assessments.

FIGURE 10: CALL FOR APPLICATIONS FOR REPOSITORY CERTIFICATION SUPPORT

The call was widely promoted via SSHOC channels and was also presented at the RDA Global Adoption Week 2020¹⁰. All of the 14 applicants were selected to receive support and join the SSHOC Certification Community (see section 4.4).

4.2.3 Call for SSH Training Community Members

In September 2019 SSHOC launched a call for the SSH Training Community at #OSFAIR2019. The idea was to form a worldwide community of SSH trainers who could collaborate to improve their professional capabilities by sharing expertise and resources. Members could sign up via the SSHOC website, and indicate their training needs, expertise and domains. The call is continuous and has onboarded 157 members to the SSH Training Community (February 2021, see section 4.4).

¹⁰ RDA Global Adoption Week 2020 <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/rda-global-adoption-week> [accessed 15.03.2021]

FIGURE 11: CALL TO JOIN THE SSH TRAINING COMMUNITY

4.2.4 SSHOC Vocabulary Survey

In February 2020 SSHOC reached out to researchers across SSH disciplines via a survey. The aim of the survey was to discover which vocabularies are the most commonly used in SSH research practice and then define a methodology to map them in alignment with the SSHOC Reference Ontology.

The survey was widely disseminated across the network and ran until May 2020. A total of 330 responses were received and analysed and further discussions were facilitated at a series of carefully documented meetings. The results were published in February 2021 in D7.6 *Resources for Marketplace Content Description*.¹¹

4.2.5 Interviews

To onboard end users from the SSH research community, SSHOC has started to work on a series of interviews with researchers. The interviews will be published to showcase the added value of SSHOC assets by peers and encourage further uptake of SSHOC assets. First interviewed were Maurizio Toscano (University of Granada) and Agnieszka Szulinska (Digital Humanities Centre at the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences). The interviews are scheduled for publication in the series **Q&A with Researchers** in March and April 2021.

¹¹ D7.6 SSHOC Resources Marketplace Content Description <https://sshopencloud.eu/d76-sshoc-resources-marketplace-content-description> [accessed 15.03.2021]

FIGURE 12: SAMPLE OF THE FIRST TWO EDITIONS OF Q&A WITH RESEARCHERS

4.3 SSHOC Communities

A further avenue for engagement has been the establishment of dedicated communities to serve researchers in specific disciplines or tasks or involve them in achieving particular objectives tied to project outputs.

4.3.1 SSH Open Marketplace Tester Community

The SSH Open Marketplace is being developed following best practice in agile and user-centered design. Its success depends on rich feedback from future users at every stage. Subsequent to the Call for SSH Marketplace Testers, (see 4.3) a dedicated SSH Open Marketplace Testers Community was set up for this purpose, and an online Consultation Platform created to facilitate the gathering of tester feedback via surveys.

A group of 39 individuals signed up as testers and contributed feedback which fed in directly to the development of the Beta version which was released in January 2021.

FIGURE 13: SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE CONSULTATION PLATFORM ON THE SSHOC WEBSITE

The SSH Open Marketplace Tester Community continues to operate, and the members are being invited to take part in dedicated engagement activities and events as development continues.

4.3.2 SSH Training Community

The call for the SSH Training Community was launched in September 2019 SSHOC at #OSFAIR2019 (see section 4.2). The idea was to form a worldwide community of SSH trainers who could collaborate to improve their professional capabilities by sharing expertise and resources.

Members sign up via the SSHOC website and are entitled to benefits including monthly meetings to share best practice, early bird access to Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps and the opportunity to contribute personal resources to the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit and advise on improvements during its implementation process. They will also have the opportunity to be included in the upcoming Trainer Directory.

At the time of writing, the community numbers more than **157 members from 43 countries**. The domain spread is illustrated below (respondents could select several domains with which they identify).

FIGURE 14: OVERVIEW OF THE SSH TRAINING COMMUNITY BY DOMAIN. MULTIPLE CHOICE WAS POSSIBLE.

4.3.3 SSHOC Certification Community

The SSHOC Certification Community numbers 14 SSH repositories whose representatives receive information and training regarding the progress of CoreTrustSeal certification. One-on-one and group consultations started in November 2020 and have already included a webinar tutorial. These interventions will continue throughout 2021.

The SSHOC certification support team works in cooperation with the FAIRsFAIR projects and related EOSC initiatives including the EOSC Executive Board Working Group Recommendations on certifying services required to enable FAIR within EOSC.

4.3.4 SSHOC Data Communities

A key feature of SSHOC is identifying practical obstacles that might interfere with the ability of end users and contributors to make optimal use of the tools and services being developed. This is achieved by working collaboratively with a small number of mutually distinctive data communities and using their experiences to arrive inductively at an understanding of difficulties which are common across disciplinary divides.

ETHNIC AND MIGRATION STUDIES

With experts undertaking research on **ethnic and migration studies**, a SSHOC task group is working to improve how quantitative survey data on Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMMs) can be shared with and discovered by a wide range of users in Europe and beyond.

During the course of the SSHOC project, this task group, in collaboration with ETHMIGSURVEYDATA and FAIRETHMIGQUANT, will produce and launch the EMM Survey Registry¹², a free online tool shaped according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles and set up to display compiled survey-level metadata for over 800 quantitative surveys across 30 countries.

Currently, in January 2021, the EMM Survey Registry is available in Beta version and displays information gathered for over **760 surveys from 18 different European countries**. Testing of an EMM-dedicated collection as part of CESSDA's European Question Bank is also underway.

ELECTION STUDIES

A second task group within SSHOC is building an open research knowledge graph in the field of electoral studies. The knowledge graph will collect, interlink, analyse, and visualise sources of information on voter participation in elections. The task is led by University of Nottingham, working together with SSHOC partners Semantic Web Company, University of Vienna/AUSSDA, and EURHISFIRM. The development and production process will serve as a pilot to assess the opportunities and challenges for similar developments in other communities, including the EURHISFIRM community.

HERITAGE SCIENCE AND HUMANITIES

Scientists from a range of disciplines – chemists, physicists, material scientists, engineers, archaeologists, digital humanists, conservators, literary scholars, historians and art historians, to name a few - collaborate in the new multidisciplinary field of heritage science. Integrating and sharing data across these fields demonstrates the need for building upon existing data and metadata standards – already developed in each scientific discipline - contributing to, reusing and connecting existing technologies rather than creating new semantic structures, authority tables and linked data. A task within SSHOC is examining how existing and future research within heritage science can use, contribute to, and be integrated within EOSC. The use case of this data community has been documented in the designed story below.

¹² EMM Survey Registry, published in Services and Tools catalogue at SSHOC website <https://sshopencloud.eu/emm-survey-registry> [accessed 15.03.2021]

FIGURE 15: SSHOC BRANDED USE CASE STORY OF THE SSHOC HERITAGE SCIENCE DATA COMMUNITY

SSHOC
social sciences & humanities open cloud

Creating a basis for multidisciplinary open linked data to save European Heritage from the digital dark ages

Societal Challenges

Thousands of different cultural heritage objects are scientifically studied, interpreted and preserved for future generations, using techniques that require complementary skills from a range of disciplines and from different institutions from all over Europe. The underlying research questions are exceptionally complex, and due to their inherent characteristics, experiments on cultural heritage artifacts are especially challenging. Opening digital data will support researchers in preserving, protecting and enhancing the significance of tangible cultural heritage. Furthermore, strengthening the cohesion of the Heritage Science digital ecosystem will foster long-term sustainability for heritage data.

Technical Challenges

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data variety - the structural heterogeneity of the data (a mix of structured, tabular, unstructured and semi-structured) means it lacks the organisation required for machine readability; No common framework and environment of FAIR data: incompatibility of data formats, heterogeneity of data representation (metadata schemas) and lack of common interdisciplinary understanding/interpretation of the data; Development and adoption of "universal" protocols and standards to generate valuable information and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> suitable metadata to be stored, accessed, queried, shared and reused among institutions, scientists and conservation professionals in various contexts and research scenarios; Exchange and creation of new knowledge across disciplines, actions, research and services put in central focus the efficient interoperability of data; Standardised and shared descriptions for analytical protocols and best practices in the field of Heritage Science.
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How EOSC can help and add value

Enabling an Open Science environment of FAIR data for European Heritage

Many institutions, organisations and projects are working to enable an Open Science environment of FAIR data for European Heritage in EOSC. Building on the experiences of PARTHENOS and ARIADNE, an international aggregation infrastructure specifically for archaeological data with a mandate to include data from the range of scientific methods in use by archaeologists, and the COST Action *Saving European Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age (SEADDA)* which is also working to build capacity for open data, including scientific data, within archaeology across Europe (and beyond), IPERION CH and IPERION HS, the Social Sciences and Humanities EOSC project SSHOC is developing an open data framework in the Heritage and Archaeological Sciences in alignment with PaNOSC, EXPANDS (through collaborative links between CERIC-ERIC and E-Rihs), and EOSC-Life. Topics being covered include 16th century Italian paintings and specifically the artist Raphael, and the analysis of archaeological remains such as human bone fragments.

A similar effort to tackle data and metadata interoperability in the heritage field was also undertaken by CLARIN-ERIC and Europeana, the European web portal which contains digitised museum collections from over 3,000 institutions across Europe. The continuing partnership between the two organisations resulted in the integration of a selection of Europeana Collections material into the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) portal.

SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #823782.

EOSC IN PRACTICE

Representatives from the above-mentioned specialist data communities participated with others in a fruitful session at the **Realising the European Open Science Cloud** conference. The session brought together thematic and interdisciplinary research communities to discuss the current situation of EOSC in practice in these communities and the 10-year outlook.

FIGURE 16: EOSC IN PRACTICE DISCUSSION DURING THE PLENARY CLOSING SESSION OF THE #REALISINGEOSC EVENT.

Fostering cross disciplinary research, and contributing to real life challenges, SSHOC is contributing behavioural data to the COVID-19 Data Platform. The use case is defined in a SSHOC branded story, to be published and promoted on the SSHOC website (see planning section 7).

FIGURE 17: SSHOC BRANDED USE CASE STORY OF THE SSHOC CONTRIBUTION TO THE COVID-19 DATA PLATFORM

SSHOC Augmenting the COVID-19 Data Platform with Behavioural data

Societal Challenges

On 20 April 2020, the European Commission together with several partners launched a European COVID-19 Data Platform to enable the rapid collection and sharing of available research data. Populating this platform with data from the Social Sciences and Humanities aims to pool and augment behavioural and attitudinal data to enable researchers to investigate the opinions and attitudes of European populations during the crisis, and monitor the occurrence and spread of the virus.

Technical Challenges

Data variety presents a challenge to the alignment of catalogues, metadata, and protocols with the life sciences and other parts of the platform. Collecting and combining quantitative and qualitative data in many formats (text, audio, video, social media) and in multiple languages requires multilingual thesauri and ontologies to make data findable and comparable; Ensuring the security and protection of sensitive data collection and analysis.

How EOSC can help and add value

Adding Social Sciences & Humanities data to the COVID-19 Data Platform, providing contextual data and a knowledge development environment

The fast-track element of the task involves the creation of a catalogue of key datasets for social, economic, psychological analyses, organised by data producer and national service provider in data hubs to replicate the EMBL structure, and supplemented with contextual economic, social, cultural, health, and migration data. The catalogue is supported with background infrastructures such as multilingual thesauri, controlled vocabularies, metadata profiles based on global standards, and data sensitivity tags.

Specific challenges for the social data are their multilinguality and large variety of data types. Qualitative data have high information value, but require specific techniques for annotations, analysis and extraction of information. Tools and expertise within the SSHOC project will be used to deal with qualitative and multimedia data and to address multilinguality.

A knowledge development track will make use of online surveys and AI techniques, focusing on the knowledge cycle and data interoperability, including non-hierarchical data, via semantic techniques such as Knowledge Graphs. To optimise reusability, concerted and collaborative actions to group and enrich data are envisioned in cooperation with research communities. Bringing relevant data together will increase efficiency, improve comparability and provide all researchers with the same opportunities for using the data. To facilitate cooperation and to provide seamless access even to sensitive data, secured environments will be set up for bringing data and researchers together.

SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #923782.

4.4 Online presence

4.4.1 Website

The SSHOC website¹³ accurately reflects project activities and is continuously updated with content and new functionality in line with developments.

In March 2020, a catalogue of existing and in-development tools and services was introduced. The catalogue offers a delivery timeline and clearly formulate individual descriptions of each item. The items are grouped by

¹³ SSHOC project website: <https://sshopencloud.eu> [accessed 15.03.2021]

category as depicted in the graphic below and displayed individually with links to associated reports and other information. The catalogue has been **viewed 1690+ times**, as measured in February 2021.

FIGURE 18: CATEGORISATION OF THE SSHOC SERVICES & TOOLS CATALOGUE

Also, in March 2020, a webpage was introduced identifying the potential beneficiaries from SSHOC and clearly explaining how the project might further their interests.

SSHOC is committed to contributing to the EOSC implementation for 2020 – 2021 with its service offering. During the six-month period between the release of the Alpha version of SSH Open Marketplace and the unveiling of the public Beta version, the website was expanded again to accommodate a dedicated consultation platform for testers.

At the time of writing, a further and very comprehensive website update exercise is nearing completion. In the process, the Training section has been considerably enhanced, text and navigation have been rethought and revisited throughout, and new content and functionality introduced. The website currently receives an average of **4345 views per month and has 253 registered users who have** subscribed to the newsletter, the Training and SSH Open Marketplace Tester Community. The website will be in a permanent state of expansion as the SSHOC project progresses and produces more results.

FIGURE 19: DATA STUDIO MONITORING DASHBOARD SHOWCASING WEBSITE TRAFFIC 2019 AND 2020

4.4.2 Brand Identity

A consistent visual identity is applied to all communication and dissemination tools. Uniformity is ensured through the use of templates for external communication. Partners also have a branding guide and a full communications kit to refer to. The contents of the communications kit are itemised below with usage figures for each.

TABLE 3: SSHOC BRANDED COMMUNICATION KIT

Item	Views	Link
SSHOC branding guidelines	372 reads	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sites/default/files/SSHOC%20Guideline booklet.pdf
SSHOC logo package	502 reads	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/logo-pack
SSHOC Press Releases (2)	461 reads	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/press-releases
Empowered by SSHOC Stamp	33 reads	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/empowered-sshoc-stamp
SSHOC infographics	62 reads	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-infographics
SSHOC Presentation	396 reads	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/presentations
Print collateral (3 items)	489 reads	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/print-collaterals-and-promotion-material

A library of branded, promotional videos has been developed and is itemised below with viewership figures.

TABLE 4: SSHOC BRANDED PROMOTIONAL VIDEOS

Video title	Views	Link
Interview with Ron Dekker, CESSDA director, SSHOC coordinator	119	https://youtu.be/gUWEragkniw
Interview with Frank Fischer, DARIAH	138	https://youtu.be/xfWuho7tVfA
Interview with Astrid Verheusen, LIBER	72	https://youtu.be/eqoCi1Cu2yY
Interview with Franciska de Jong, CLARIN-ERIC	175	https://youtu.be/cgJbOgfXvzY
Marketplace Matej Ďurčo ÖAW ACDH	11	https://youtu.be/-TmorX0WGWY
Dataverse Marion Wittenberg DANS KNAW	44	https://youtu.be/ObfGIO78RSM
Launch of the SSHOC Training Community - Interview with Ellen Leenarts at OS Fair 2019	95	https://youtu.be/DWuHgQGKhDA
SSH Open Marketplace - explained the easy way	7400	https://youtu.be/4tyZ4vhrM9s
Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud	185	https://youtu.be/UP7dBiV3-yQ

Specific branding of the SSHOC services has been developed making their look and feel homogeneous under the SSHOC umbrella. SSHOC-owned and maintained services and tools are branded with the SSHOC identity. Those which have been further enhanced under SSHOC but are owned and will be maintained by partners are branded with an “**empowered by SSHOC**” stamp.

FIGURE 20: STAMP CREATED TO BRAND SERVICES & TOOLS ENHANCED BY SSHOC, BUT OWNED AND MAINTAINED BY SSHOC PARTNERS

4.4.3 Social Media

As defined in D2.1 *Communication and Overall Outreach Plan*¹⁴, the social media strategy aims to disseminate project results and activities in a content-rich and engaging manner with support from the partner network and strategic multipliers to increase visibility and impact. In collaboration with WP6, live tweeting is a feature of webinars, events and conference sessions.

SSHOC has a strong social media following, with **1410 followers on Twitter** and **384 connections on LinkedIn**.

During 2020, two collaborative “Twitter Takeovers”, one with LIBER and the other with DARIAH, helped grow follower numbers.

FIGURE 21: SSHOC BRANDED PROMOTIONAL BANNER FOR TWITTER TAKEOVER

The LIBER takeover in February 2020 highlighted work on interoperability via a focus on D3.1 Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems¹⁵. Interoperability expert Mari Kleemola (FSD) presided.

¹⁴ Annika Schwabe, Julian Ausserhofer, Leonardo Marino, Marieke Willems, Vasso Kalaitzi, Irena Vipavc Bvrar, ... Silvana Muscella. (2019). SSHOC D2.1 Overall Communication and Outreach Plan (approved 18 nov 2019) (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3595935.

¹⁵ Broeder, Daan, Trippel, Thorsten, Degl'Innocenti, Emiliano, Giacomini, Roberta, Sanesi, Maurizio, Kleemola, Mari, ... Đurčo, Matej. (2019). SSHOC D3.1 Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems (Version v1.0). Zenodo.. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3569868

The DARIAH takeover launched the Alpha release of the SSH Open Marketplace and featured WP lead and DARIAH director Frank Fischer.

Between them the takeovers **published 60 tweets**, engaged **150+ followers** and received **35K views** in total. The full tweet sequences are available for view at [#SSHOCifyDARIAH](#) and [#SSHOCCLIBERTakeover](#).

A SSHOC CLARIN Twitter Takeover is planned for June 2021 preceding the ICTeSSH2021 pre-conference workshop on the SSHOC Vocabulary Initiative.

4.5 SSHOC Publications

SSHOC engages its end user communities through publications, being scientific, white papers and publications in external channels to raise awareness on SSHOC assets and foster adoption. The scientific publications are accessible via the dedicated webpage on the project website, currently twelve publications are highlighted¹⁶.

FIGURE 22: SAMPLE OF SSHOC SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS ON DEDICATED PAGE OF THE PROJECT WEBSITE.

<p>Mining Wages in Nineteenth-Century Job Advertisements. The Application of Language Resources and Language Technology to study Economic and Social Inequality</p> <p>For the analysis of historical wage development, no structured data is available. Job advertisements, as found in newspapers...</p> <p>Read more 15 June 2020</p>		
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In addition, a series of SSHOC-branded white papers has been published on Zenodo and is available via the SSHOC website. The itemised table appears below.

¹⁶ SSHOC scientific publications webpage: <https://sshopencloud.eu/scientific-publications> [accessed 15.03.2021]

TABLE 5: SSHOC BRANDED WHITE PAPERS

Report	Views	Link
Response from SSHOC on COVID-19	201 reads on the website 31 views, 62 downloads on Zenodo	https://sshopencloud.eu/response-sshoc-covid-19
SSHOC - Position paper 2020	296 reads on the website 80 views, 74 downloads on Zenodo	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-position-paper-2020
ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC	215 reads on the website 1147 views, 964 downloads on Zenodo	https://sshopencloud.eu/esfri-cluster-projects-position-papers-expectations-and-planned-contributions-eosc

The SSHOC consortium has also presented fully branded and audience-tailored posters. Eight posters have been published on Zenodo for future reuse.

TABLE 6: SSHOC BRANDED POSTERS

Conference	Poster title	Views	Link
EOSC-hub week 2019	Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities for the European Open Science Cloud - EOSC Hub	Website: 260 views Zenodo: 107 views, 33 downloads	doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3626959
LIBER 2019	Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities part of the European Open Science Cloud - Liber	Website: 309 views Zenodo: 47 views, 31 downloads	https://zenodo.org/record/36330
CLARIN Annual Conference	Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities for the European Open Science Cloud - CLARIN	Website: 266 views Zenodo: 29 views, 23 downloads	doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3633038
EOSC Symposium 2019	A Marketplace for the Social Sciences and Humanities	Website: 300 views Zenodo: 172 views, 99 downloads	doi:10.5281/zenodo.3550956
Open Science Fair 2019	Social Sciences and Humanities Community Building: Training - Open Science FAIR	Website: 286 views Zenodo: 50 views, 42 downloads	doi:10.5281/zenodo.3633058
FAIR principles and user feedback on the SSH Open Marketplace 2020	FAIR research data in the Social Sciences and Humanities	Website: 373 views Zenodo: 57 views, 87 downloads	doi:10.5281/zenodo.3686776
EOSC-hub week 2020	Three Pillars of the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace	Website: 352 views Zenodo: 223 views, 134 downloads	doi:10.5281/zenodo.3550957
Open Science Conference 2021	A Training Discovery Toolkit for the Social Sciences and Humanities - OpenScience Conference2021 - February 2021	Website: 6 views Zenodo: 205 views, 62 downloads	doi: 10.5281/zenodo.453419

5. Outreach to the Greater EOSC Community

The vision of the EOSC is to provide seamless, Europe-wide access to research data and tools across scientific or thematic disciplines and geographical borders. It is thus incumbent on each thematic cluster to create synergies, leverage cross-cutting tasks, share best practices, and engage stakeholders jointly in the interest of fostering cross-disciplinary research.

FIGURE 23: BLOMBERG, NIKLAS, & PETZOLD, ANDREAS. (2020, JANUARY 30). ESFRI THEMATIC CLUSTER VIEW ON EOSC. ZENODO. [HTTP://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.3631247](http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3631247)

European Open Science Cloud =

5.1 SSHOC and the EOSC Thematic Clusters

The table below details the efforts made by the SSHOC project to create synergies and the results obtained.

TABLE 7: SSHOC SYNERGIES WITH EOSC CLUSTER PROJECTS

Synergy	Output	Impact
SSHOC Kick-off meeting	Discussion panel at SSHOC Kick-off meeting: https://sshopencloud.eu/news/where-social-sciences-and-humanities-meet-european-open-science-cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendees +100 News item viewed over 900 times.
RDA P14	Session “EOSC, ESFRI Cluster Projects, RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services” News and report: https://sshopencloud.eu/news/eosc-esfri-cluster-projects-rda%C2%A0connecting-commonalities-and-collaborative-solutions-community Event item: https://sshopencloud.eu/eosc-services-collaborations-and-rda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Session attended by 40+ participants News item viewed 860+ times Event item viewed 680 times Report viewed 204 times Report downloaded 244 times
3-monthly communication & stakeholder meetings as of January 2020	Cross-project promotion & sharing of information.	4 meetings in 2020
ESFRI Cluster Position Papers on EOSC Implementation	Paper: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-cluster-position-papers-eosc-implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Content viewed on SSHOC website: 220+ times Position paper downloaded 957 times Position paper viewed 1138 times
Joint submission ICT2020	Joint proposal ICT2020 stand” The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures: A cross-disciplinary approach to EOSC - ICT 2020 has been cancelled	N/A
“Realising EOSC” conference	Joint session “ <i>Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud</i> ” Presentation: https://zenodo.org/record/4277601#.YAWk2C2ZO1t Recordings: https://youtu.be/jpWU9qVnY5o	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Realising EOSC event attended by 690+ people Session recording viewed 22 times Presentation viewed 44 times Presentation downloaded 34 times
Joint session proposal submitted for RDA Plenary 17	“ <i>The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons. Debating commonalities and collaboration for thematic services, training and governance towards the European Open Science Cloud</i> ”	Awaiting acceptance at the writing of this deliverable, February 2021.

5.2 Building on Solid ERIC Ground

SSHOC is founded on an extensive existing network of European Research Infrastructure Consortia in the social sciences and humanities. The table below summarises the outreach activities of these realities to date with the corresponding engagement numbers.

TABLE 8: ERICS IN SSHOC CHANNELS

ESFRI	Community domain	Community in numbers	Twitter followers	LinkedIn connections	Newsletter subscribers	Annual events attendance rate	Website visits
CESSDA-ERIC	Social Science	22 members countries	2647	310	2 newsletters per month 457 subscribers	4 per year, attended by representatives of all 22 members and service providers	8K average monthly visits (2020)
CLARIN - ERIC	European Research Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technology	20 member countries, 4 observers and 1 third party. 7400 researchers participated to 2019 User involvement activities	3625	220	12 newsletters per year - 1421 subscribers	1 Annual event with around 250 participants (2019, F2F event). 2020 virtual event 500 participants.	8.4K average monthly visits
DARIAH - ERIC	Digital Research Infrastructure for Arts and Humanities	19 member countries, 1 observer country, 17 Cooperating Partners. 9,925 event attendees in 2019 DARIAH events.	8469	80	12 newsletters per year - 720 subscribers	1 Annual event with around 250 participants (2019, physical event). 2020 virtual event c. 500 participants	2.5K monthly visits
ESS-ERIC	European Social Survey	7 core scientific team institutes; 25 member countries; 1 observer country; 3 guest countries in Round 9	14.1K	991	3 newsletters per year – 12,000 subscribers	250-300 attendees at international conference, held every three years	32K monthly visits (2020 average)
E-RIHS ERIC	Heritage Science	20 partners and 160 project members	684	41	no newsletters	1 annual event per year, participated	2.2K monthly visits

ESFRI	Community domain	Community in numbers	Twitter followers	LinkedIn connections	Newsletter subscribers	Annual events attendance rate	Website visits
						by all members (60-80 attendees)	
SHARE - ERIC	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe	28 European countries and Israel joined SHARE, 10,368 registered users	1281	N/A	2 newsletters per year	4 end-user workshops per year (2019)	N/D

5.3 SSHOC and Other EOSC Projects

In addition to the synergies created with the ESFRI cluster projects, SSHOC has sought to engage with user communities through collaboration with other EOSC projects from the groups depicted in the infographic below.

FIGURE 24: SSHOC IN THE EOSC ECOSYSTEM

The table below details the efforts made by the SSHOC project to create cross-disciplinary synergies and the results obtained.

TABLE 9: SSHOC SYNERGIES BUILT IN THE EOSC ECOSYSTEM

Synergy	Output	Impact
EOSC Secretariat	<p>SSHOC second consortium meeting presentation</p> <p>ESFRI Cluster Position Papers on EOSC Implementation</p> <p>Article publication in LR4SSHOC proceedings: https://sshopencloud.eu/eosc-game-changer-social-sciences-and-humanities-research-activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 70 people present Impact position paper see (see synergies ESFRI cluster project section 5.1) LR4SSHOC article, 380+ reads on SSHOC website
EOSC-hub & FREYA	<p>Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH. Joint 4-day conference with EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC: https://sshopencloud.eu/realising-european-open-science-cloud</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 690+ Participants, from 45 countries, including from 20 countries outside the EU 33 booths from EOSC projects, visited over 3780 times, 880 video views, 1520 document views
RDA and RDA Europe 4.0	<p>RDA Plenaries & events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RDA P13 presentation in Social Science Research Data Interest Group RDA P14 EOSC services, collaborations, and RDA workshop & report Presentation of SSHOC Certification support and plan RDA Global adoption week 2020 & adoption story: https://sshopencloud.eu/rda-global-adoption-week Session RDA P16 SSHOC presentation RDA Slovenia event 	<p>RDA P13 session, 75 attendees</p> <p>RDA P14 impact see section 5.1</p> <p>RDA global adoption week:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100 attendees over 2 sessions recordings viewed 40 times
	<p>Presentation RDA Europe at SSHOC 2nd consortium meeting</p>	<p>Over 70 participants</p>
	<p>Input RDA for EOSC survey report: Bangert, Daniel, Fava, Ilaria, O'Connor, Ryan, Jones, Sarah, Delipalta, Alex, Garavelli, Sara, & Biro, Timea. (2020). Report on RDA integration with other European initiatives (Version v1.0_draft). DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3630264.</p> <p>news: https://www.rd-alliance.org/research-data-alliance-contributing-european-open-science-cloud</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report viewed 303 times Report downloaded 220 times
	<p>SSHOC RDA adoption story <i>The RDA CoreTrustSeal adoption story across domains and regions - SSHOC is one of the 9 stories told:</i> https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-coretrustseal-adoption-story-across-domains-and-regions</p>	<p>Adoption story page viewed 2684 times</p>
	<p>SSHOC RDA adoption story <i>The Ethnic And Migrant Minorities' (EMMs') Survey Registry: A Tool To Help Make EMM Survey Data FAIR:</i> https://www.rd-alliance.org/ethnic-and-migrant-minorities-emms-survey-registry-tool-help-make-emm-survey-data-fair</p>	<p>Story viewed 268 times</p>

Synergy	Output	Impact
	<p>SSHOC series of two articles on RDA for social sciences</p> <p><i>How the RDA impacts social sciences research (and what's in it for SSHOC):</i> https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/how-rda-impacts-social-sciences-research-and-what's-it-sshoc</p> <p><i>How the RDA impacts SSHOC (Feedback from Project Partners):</i> https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/how-rda-impacts-sshoc-feedback-project-partners</p>	No Data
	<p>Joint session at “Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH” conference.</p> <p><i>Community Building Examples Across EOSC-hub, FREYA, & SSHOC</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> slides: https://zenodo.org/communities/realisingtheeoscevent/search?page=1&size=20 Recordings: https://youtu.be/BELr6kG-bnk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conference attended by 690+ people Slide decks viewed 56 times, downloaded 45 times Recordings viewed 14 times
EOSC-hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SSHOC highlight in EOSC-hub magazine: https://www.eosc-hub.eu/news/eosc-hub-magazine-issue-3 EOSC-hub week 2019 session presentation: https://sshopencloud.eu/news/my-cloud-your-cloud-our-cloud EOSC hub week 2019 poster: Kalaitzi, Vasso, & Willems, Marieke. (2020). Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities for the European Open Science Cloud - EOSC Hub (Version v1.0). Presented at the EOSC Hub Week 2019, Prague: Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3626960 EOSC-hub week 2020 poster: https://www.eosc-hub.eu/eosc-hub-week-2020-poster-voting SSHOC Task Force on EOSC alignment, resulting in two EOSC-hub & SSHOC joint sessions during #Realising EOSC event SSHOC Task Force on EOSC alignment, resulting in two EOSC-hub & SSHOC joint sessions during #Realising EOSC event: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboarding services to the EOSC portal at #Realising EOSC event https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/how-can-i-onboard-my-resource-eosc# Thematic Services for Social Sciences and Humanities & SSHOC WP3 Lifting Technologies into the SSH Cloud #Realising EOSC event: https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/thematic-services-social-sciences-and-humanities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC-hub week 2019 session attended by 100 people, news-item read 394 times EOSC-hub week poster 2019: 106 views, 32 downloads EOSC-hub week poster 2020: 220 views, 131 downloads Session recordings at #Realising EOSC event recordings viewed 57 times
EOSC DIH	<p>Joint session during #Realising EOSC event. “Engaging the Private Sector. About roadblocks and success stories in the uptake</p>	<p>Session recording viewed 9 times. Follow-up meeting on partnership</p>

Synergy	Output	Impact
	of EOSC services". https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/engaging-private-sector-about-roadblocks-and-success-stories-uptake-eosc-services	for exploitation of SSHOC tools & services took place in December 2020.
OPERAS & TRIPLE	<p>Joint communication efforts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SSHOC participation & presentation Kick-Off meeting Triple Project ● Regular communication meetings, series of three joint articles & infographics planned for March, April, May 2021 ● Article publication in LR4SSHOC proceedings. "Social Sciences and Humanities Pathway Towards the European Open Science Cloud": https://sshopencloud.eu/social-sciences-and-humanities-pathway-towards-european-open-science-cloud <p>Joint events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FAIR Research Data Management in SSH: a CO-OPERAS IN & SSHOC Workshop: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ report: Buddenbohm, Stefan, Barthauer, Raisa, & Dung, Joseph. (2020, February 25). FAIR research data in the Social Sciences and Humanities (Version v1.0). Presented at the FAIR principles and user feedback on the SSH Open Marketplace, Göttingen, Germany: Zenodo. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3686777 ○ news: https://sshopencloud.eu/news/fair-principles-and-user-feedback-ssh-open-marketplace ● <i>Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC</i>, joint session at "Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH" conference. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ slides: Frank Fischer, Yoann Moranville, Laure Barbot, Laurent Capelli, Virginie Ngo, Suzanne Dumouchel, ... Tomasz Parkoła. (2020, November). Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC. Presented at the REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences, humanities and beyond, Zenodo. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4290599 ○ recordings: https://youtu.be/hr94Yz8odPE 	LR4SSHOC article received 440 reads on the SSHOC website. <p>CO-OPERAS IN & SSHOC workshop:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● report viewed 55 times ● report downloaded 85 times ● news viewed 230 times <p><i>Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● recordings viewed 17 times. ● slides viewed 22 times, downloaded 10 times.

Synergy	Output	Impact
FAIRs FAIR	<p>Synergies on communication tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation SSHOC 2nd consortium meeting: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/2nd-sshoc-consortium-meeting • FAIRsFAIR video “How FAIR is research in Europe Today?” https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7JwO_tXXqKc • Joint co-located event submission RDA P17 <p>SSHOC representation in FAIRsFAIR synchronisation workshops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSHOC FAIR champion Ersébet Toth: https://fairsfair.eu/advisory-board/egfc • Input D3.6 Proposal on integration of metadata catalogues to support cross-disciplinary FAIR uptake: https://zenodo.org/record/4134788#.YC-l8i2ZO1s • Collaboration on SSHOC T8.2, Certification support of trusted SSH repositories. 	<p>2nd Consortium Meeting 70 attendees</p> <p>426 views video</p> <p>FAIRsFAIR D3.6 received 419 views, 326 downloads</p>
Europeana	<p>Europeana 2019 Pre-conference Workshop: EOSC's Evolutionary Scenarios - New Perspectives for Digital Cultural Heritage https://www.sshopencloud.eu/europeana-2019-eosc-digital-cultural-heritage</p> <p><i>Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?</i> joint session at “Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH” conference.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • slides: https://zenodo.org/communities/realisingtheeoscevent/se-arch?page=1&size=20 • recordings: https://youtu.be/iqHwZNOaLsU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Science session recordings viewed 43 times • follow-up session submitted for LIBER2021
EOSCEnhance	<p>SSHOC Task Force on EOSC alignment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input for EOSCEnhance D5.2 EOSC Portal requirements: https://eosc-portal.eu/sites/default/files/D5.2%20EOSC%20Portal%20requirements%20v1.0%20FINAL.pdf <p>2 Joint sessions at “Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH” conference.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud • How can I onboard my resource to EOSC? 	<p>Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud (see impact under ESFRI clusters)</p> <p>How can I onboard my resource to EOSC? (see impact under EOSC-hub)</p>

30 EOSC-related projects were also actively engaged in EOSC EXPO at the joint #RealisingEOSC conference. The projects are identified in the image below.

FIGURE 25: 30 PROJECTS ENGAGED AT THE EOSC EXPO OF THE #REALISINGEOSC CONFERENCE

5.4 Onboarding Research Funders, Citizen Scientists and Policymakers

Clearly, a solid network has been established with researchers, universities, libraries, and EOSC initiatives. Effort towards research funding institutions, the private sector and industry, policymakers, and citizens and citizen scientists is detailed in this section of the report.

5.4.1 Research Funding Institutions

Research funding institutions such as the EC have been specifically invited to a number of SSHOC events. These include:

- EOSC, ESFRI Cluster Projects, RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services session at RDA Plenary 14¹⁷.
- The #RealisingEOSC conference in November 2020: Liina Munari, European Commission Communications Networks, Content and Technology Directorate-General - elnfrastructure and

¹⁷ SSHOC announcement RDA P14 co-located session with RDA and EOSC cluster projects:

<https://sshopencloud.eu/news/eosc-esfri-cluster-projects-rda%C2%A0connecting-commonalities-and-collaborative-so> [accessed 15.03.2021]

European Open Science Cloud Deputy Head of Unit was invited to deliver the keynote at the opening session¹⁸.

SSHOC also attended EC- organised meetings:

- DG Connect and DG RTD meeting with EOSC projects¹⁹ in September 2019.
- Dedicated meeting between EC and SSHOC Tier 1 members in December 2020.

5.4.2 Private Sector and Industry

In addition to the two SMEs involved in the consortium, the **#RealisingEOSC** session on *“Engaging the Private Sector About roadblocks and success stories in the uptake of EOSC”*²⁰ initiated the conversation on onboarding the private sector and industry through collaboration with the EOSC DIH.

FIGURE 26: ENGAGING THE PRIVATE SECTOR. ABOUT ROADBLOCKS AND SUCCESS STORIES IN THE UPTAKE OF EOSC SESSION #REALISINGEOSC CONFERENCE

¹⁸ Announcement Realising EOSC event: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/agenda> [accessed 15.03.2021]

¹⁹ DG Connect and DG RTD meeting with EOSC projects <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/building-eosc-through-h2020-projects> [accessed 15.03.2021]

²⁰ Engaging the Private Sector About roadblocks and success stories in the uptake of EOSC <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/engaging-private-sector-about-roadblocks-and-success-stories-uptake-eosc-services> [accessed 15.03.2021]

5.4.3 Citizens and Citizen Scientists

The session *Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?* at the **Realising EOOSC** conference explored the potential for citizens and citizen scientists to participate in scientific progress via open SSH data. The session was co-organised with Europeana, the LIBER Citizen Science Working Group and citizen science projects *The Bentham Project* and the *Transcribathon*²¹.

FIGURE 27: CITIZEN SCIENCE: WHAT IT MEANS FOR SSH AND HOW CAN MULTIDISCIPLINARITY BE ACHIEVED?

5.4.4 Policymakers

As we see in section 2, policymakers could benefit from SSHOC tools & services as end users of the SSHOC assets. During the RDA Plenary 14 event on EOOSC services, collaborations and the RDA, EC policymakers were invited and actively contributed to the recommendations, available in the post event report *EOOSC. ESFRI Cluster Projects. RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services*²². The news item was read over 900 times, and the report available on Zenodo was viewed 208 times and downloaded 227 times.

During the midterm review²³ the consortium was advised to increase engagement with this stakeholder group in the latter half of the project. The four-day Realising EOOSC event, organised during November 2020 in cooperation with FREYA and EOOSC-hub, provided SSHOC with the opportunity to strengthen relationships with policymakers. Liina Munari from the European Commission Communications Networks, Content and Technology Directorate-General was welcomed as a keynote speaker and an additional six policymakers attended the conference.

²¹ Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved? <https://www.eoosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/citizen-science-what-it-means-ssh-and-how-can-multidisciplinary-be-achieved> [accessed 15.03.2021]

²² EOOSC. ESFRI Cluster Projects. RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/eoosc-esfri-cluster-projects-rda%C2%A0connecting-commonalities-and-collaborative-solutions-community> [accessed 15.03.2021]

²³ SSHOC Aces Annual Project review: <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-aces-annual-project-review> [accessed 15.03.2021]

6. Onboarding End Users in the remaining months of the SSHOC project

Now at month 27 in the project, SSHOC has many tools and services already delivered and more coming on stream, ready for uptake by end users. Until the end of the project in April 20202, the aim is to intensify dissemination and engagement efforts around the SSHOC exploitable assets in order to grow user numbers significantly.

In October 2020, the EOSC Executive Board published the 8th version of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)²⁴. The document identifies Actors in the EOSC ecosystem and related skills needs. Each role is further elaborated in the report on Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science, published by the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group in February 2021²⁵.

The report states that the Framework of Actors in the EOSC Ecosystem identifies roles, rather than job titles, as it is likely that in some cases the same person could undertake different roles (e.g., trainer and researcher, data scientist and research software engineer, etc.). The functions and actions undertaken by each role are considered to be representative rather than exhaustive due to the constant evolution in this area. The roles identified address the needs of stakeholders from the whole EOSC landscape, including research infrastructures, technology providers, service providers, data managers, researchers, policy makers (including funders), and citizens in general.

Until the end of the project, SSHOC will align with the definition of roles as mapped in the EOSC SRIA (figure 24), fostering targeted onboarding of end users. SSHOC will do this by aligning the identification of the engaged communities and tailor the target messages accordingly.

²⁴ Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc-sria-v08.pdf> [accessed 15.03.2021]

²⁵ Report on Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science, published by the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group in February 2021: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/af7f7807-6ce1-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190694287> [accessed 15.03.2021]

FIGURE 28: FRAMEWORK OF ACTORS IN THE EOSC ECOSYSTEM

6.1 SSH Researchers, Universities and Research Performing Institutions

Researchers represent the key user group. Planned outreach to this group will be focused primarily on fostering uptake of SSHOC services and tools. Key activities are summarised in the table below.

TABLE 10: ONBOARDING OF SSH RESEARCHERS, UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH PERFORMING INSTITUTIONS STRATEGY FOR M27-M40

Aim	Activity	KPI by M40
Provide information	Create a downloadable factsheet for each item in the Tools and Services Catalogue and publish full series in the project communications kit.	SSHOC branded factsheets for services or tools 1 booklet of factsheets 1 social media campaign
	Package factsheets with associated sales information, Q&As and recordings and create a single, consolidated, downloadable Researcher & SSHOC resource. For use at the upcoming end-user event.	1 consolidated sales package 1 social media campaign
	Showcase SSHOC vocabulary in a dedicated session at ICTeSSH 2021.	1 session, engaging researchers 1 slidedeck 1 recording 1 conference proceedings publication 1 social media campaign
	Carefully brand all SSHOC services & tools, through SSHOC branding or Empowered by SSHOC stamp.	all SSHOC assets carefully branded
	Publish a series of joint articles with TRIPLE, highlighting SSH services & tools for researchers.	1 series of 3 articles 1 social media campaign 1 series of infographics
Profile early adopters.	Create a dedicated Q&A section on SSHOC website, compile and publish Q&As with end users in written or podcast format.	8 Q&As with researchers 1 social media campaign
	Create dedicated Use Case section on SSHOC website, compile and publish use case stories related to services and tools	5 use cases 1 social media campaign
Engage users	Provide SSH Open Marketplace Tester community with regular updates on newly delivered SSHOC services & tools.	1 update every 2 months
	Invite SSHOC Data Communities to policymaker focused event, fostering the use of SSH data and SSHOC tools and services.	1 event 1 social media campaign 1 recording 1 policy brief with recommendations for policymakers

Aim	Activity	KPI by M40
	Organise a series of awareness raising events, targeted at all end user categories, in alignment with WP6	1 series of stakeholder engagement awareness raising events

6.2 EOSC and Research e-Infrastructures

Planned activities to support joint alignment with the EOSC thematic clusters and Research e-Infrastructures on a common governance model for the treatment of thematic data, and to attract end users are summarised in the table below.

TABLE 11: ONBOARDING EOSC AND RESEARCH E-INFRASTRUCTURES STRATEGY FOR M27-M40

Aim	Activity	KPI by M40
Provide information	Create a downloadable factsheet for each item in the Tools and Services Catalogue and publish full series as a booklet.	1 booklet of factsheets (see above)
	SSHOC workshop: SSH Code of Conduct	1 meeting and package of resources
Engage EOSC and e-Infrastructures on alignment of cross-cutting work. Foster cross-disciplinary research	RDA Plenary 17 joint session " <i>The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons. Debating commonalities and collaboration for thematic services, training and governance towards the European Open Science Cloud</i> " submitted.	1 joint session with Thematic clusters and FAIRsFAIR
	Joint final stakeholder conference	1 conference 1 collection of presentations, recordings and conference resources
Foster EOSC in Practice	Showcase SSHOC tools for RIs at ERIC annual events	1 series of SSHOC dedicated sessions at 2021 and 2022 ERIC annual meetings

6.3 Research Libraries and Archives

From the perspective of training in particular, both as regards attendance at events and representation within the SSH Training Community, research librarians and data support staff are key influencers within the SSH research landscape. Over the next 12 months and in order to foster uptake of SSHOC services & tools through research libraries & archives, SSHOC will continue to build the strong relationship which has been established with research libraries. An overview of planned activities appears in the table below.

TABLE 12: ONBOARDING RESEARCH LIBRARIES AND ARCHIVES STRATEGY M27-M40

Aim	Activity	KPI by M40
Provide information	Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps	continue series of bootcamps
	SSHOC series of SSH Training Community meetings	continue meetings on a monthly basis
	SSHOC & LIBER Citizen Science WG coordinated session at LIBER 2021: <i>Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?</i> submitted.	1 joint session at LIBER 2021
	SSHOC poster presentation on the SSH Open Marketplace at LIBER 2021	1 poster at LIBER 2021 1 poster upload on Zenodo 1 social media campaign
	LIBER2021 session on Encoding theatrical text collections for discovery, exploration, and visualisation; the added value of SSHOC/CLARIN services.	1 joint session at LIBER 2021

6.4 Research Funders

SSHOC adds value to Research Funders by providing access to national and institutional data scalable at a European level and ensuring an easier management of IPRs and ethical issues as a result of harmonised data policies.

TABLE 13: ONBOARDING RESEARCH LIBRARIES AND ARCHIVES STRATEGY FOR M27-M40

Aim	Activity	KPI by M40
Showcase added value of SSHOC with Funders on national and European level	Identify funders for targeted invitations to SSHOC events and ERICs annual meetings and tailored messaging on SSHOC assets.	At least 10 identified national and European funders for SSHOC & ERIC events.
	Showcase the need for SSH certified repositories for trusted research, a requirement for research funders.	1 dedicated space on the website to highlight the added value of certified repositories.

6.5 Private Sector and Industry

SSHOC provides the private sector and industry with access to promotional and new business opportunities via the SSH Open Marketplace and a means of interacting with researchers to improve service quality.

With the **#RealisingEOSC** session on “Engaging the Private Sector About roadblocks and success stories in the uptake of EOSC”²⁶ SSHOC initiated the conversation on onboarding the private sector and industry through collaboration with the EOSC DIH. The table below includes the next steps for this conversation.

As already defined in D6.2, SSHOC has started a conversation with ARCHIVER²⁷ in February 2021, about adopting the ARCHIVER services. With a total procurement budget of 3.4 million euros, ARCHIVER will use a Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) approach to competitively source R&D services in three stages: design, prototyping and pilot. The resulting services will become part of the EOSC catalogue.

TABLE 14: ONBOARDING INDUSTRY AND THE PRIVATE SECTOR STRATEGY FOR M27-M40

Aim	Activity	KPI by M40
Foster adoption of SSHOC results with Industry & private sector	Define clear route to partnership with EOSC DIH.	1 partnership signed with EOSC DIH
Foster collaboration with SMEs and start-ups	Engage SME in development of gamified research data management tools.	1 SME collaboration through jointly developed RDM tool for researchers
Identify a potential collaboration between ARCHIVER and SSHOC	Working meeting with ARCHIVER project, to identify early adopters of the ARCHIVER services in the SSH domain.	1 working meeting in the shape of a webinar

6.6 Citizens and Citizen Scientists

Citizens and citizen scientists benefit from SSHOC through opportunities to participate in scientific progress via access to SSH data and by using tools developed by the project. To continue to onboard this end user group, a follow up workshop from the *Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?* at the **Realising EOSC conference** has been submitted for the LIBER 2021 conference in June 2021.

²⁶ Engaging the Private Sector About roadblocks and success stories in the uptake of EOSC <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/engaging-private-sector-about-roadblocks-and-success-stories-uptake-eosc-services> [accessed 15.03.2021]

²⁷ ARCHIVER project website: <https://www.archiver-project.eu> [accessed 15.03.2021]

TABLE 15: ONBOARDING CITIZENS AND CITIZEN SCIENTISTS STRATEGY FOR M27-M40

Aim	Activity	KPI by M40
SSHOC & LIBER Citizen Science WG coordinated workshop at LIBER 2021: <i>Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?</i> submitted.	1 session at LIBER 2021	1 citizen science targeted session + resources 1 social media campaign
Showcase citizen science initiatives in SSHOC network	Q&A with LIBER Citizen Science WG	1 Q&A 1 social media campaign

6.7 Policymakers

As detailed in section 2, SSHOC provides added value to policymakers through:

- Access to national and institutional data scalable at a European level
- Easier management of IPRs and ethical issues as a result of harmonised data policies
- Access to reports on legislative or interoperability issues affecting data handling across geographical and disciplinary borders

A dedicated session for policymakers is foreseen. The event will focus on access to national and institutional data scalable at a European level, easier management of IPRs, and ethical issues as a result of harmonised data policies and access to reports on legislative or interoperability issues affecting data handling across geographical and disciplinary borders. In this case the three SSH Data Communities, Ethnic Minorities and Migration, Election Studies, and the Austrian Corona Panel Project will serve as examples.

TABLE 16: ONBOARDING POLICYMAKERS STRATEGY FOR M27-M40

Aim	Activity	KPI by M40
Showcase the added value of SSHOC Data Communities for policymakers	1 stand-alone online session showcasing SSH Data Communities. Ethnic Minorities and Migration, Election Studies, and the Austrian Corona Panel Project will serve as examples in the discussion with policymakers on data driven policymaking.	1 session 1 slidedeck 1 recording on YouTube 1 social media campaign 1 post-event report with recommendations for policy makers
Showcase policymakers in SSHOC network	Q&A with policymaker (identified at the policymaker event)	1 Q&A 1 social media campaign

6.8 Monitoring Impact: Progress Against Targets

In D2.1 *Overall Communication and Outreach Plan* a series of KPIs was defined. The table below details the progress against targets as at M26, and defines the targets for M27-M40.

TABLE 17: KPI MONITORING AND ROADMAP M27-M40

Mechanism	Communication tool	KPIs (total numbers over 40 months)	Status February 2021	March 2021 – April 2022
Communication Toolbox	Webinars	8 webinars 1000 views >30 registered participants per webinar	KPI over-achieved with: 16 webinars >2600+ views of recordings >75+ average registered participants	
	Newsletter	20 newsletters 400 subscribers Opening rate of 25% per newsletter	KPI on track: 7 newsletters 330 subscribers 46% av. open rate	1 newsletter per month actively search for additional subscribers through event registration
	Print material	2 roll up banners (1 general, 1 marketplace) 5 brochures (1 general, 1 marketplace, 3 pilot studies)	KPI achieved with: 1 roll-up banner 1 flier 9 posters 2 Q&As with researchers	No additional roll-up banners foreseen as there is no use for this due to COVID-19 Restrictions for F2F meetings. A series of factsheets & Use Case fliers is foreseen At least 1 additional poster for LIBER 2021
	Presentation	1 PowerPoint template 1 PowerPoint general information presentations (regularly updated)	KPI achieved: 1 ppt template 1 general ppt presentation 1 presentation for the SSHOC mid-term review, accessible via Zenodo 1 series of ppt presentations uploaded to Zenodo	Updates where needed

Mechanism	Communication tool	KPIs (total numbers over 40 months)	Status February 2021	March 2021 – April 2022
	Document templates	1 template for internal and public deliverables 1 template for external communication	KPI achieved: 1 template for internal and public deliverables 1 template for project reports	Updates when needed
	Press releases	6 (launch, marketplace, etc.)	2 press releases	4 additional press releases foreseen -final release SSH Open Marketplace (December 2021) -SSHOC Vocabulary Initiative (prior to ICTeSSH, and CLARIN twitter takeover, June 2021) -Access to Data Catalogues in updated website (April 2021) -SSHOC final event (Autumn 2021) -SSHOC services & tools booklet of factsheets (Summer 2021)
Web presence	Website with Marketplace	800 views/month	KPI achieved with: 2000+ views per month in the last year	Continue with content- rich publications on SSHOC website
	News pieces on website	>40 pieces	KPI over-achieved with 78 news-items 29 Deliverables 94 events 21 services & tools (online catalogue)	Continue with content- rich publications on SSHOC website
Digital community interaction	Twitter	>900 Tweets 30.000 impressions/month	KPI achieved with 1052 tweets, and 47.000 impressions in M21.	Continue continuous social media campaign & scouting connections
	LinkedIn	>900 LinkedIn Posts 1 LinkedIn article per month	KPI for LinkedIn: 62 LinkedIn posts Underperforming, as Twitter seems by far a	In M6 SSHOC moved to a company profile account, this means the article publishing

Mechanism	Communication tool	KPIs (total numbers over 40 months)	Status February 2021	March 2021 – April 2022
			better engagement mechanism for the EOSC and SSH communities.	feature is no longer available SSHOC will actively scout LinkedIn connections to increase engagement on LinkedIn Additional 100 posts on LinkedIn M26-M40
Physical events and local activities	Conferences	3 (Kick-off, mid-project stakeholder forum, final conference) >100 per conference All stakeholder groups should be represented at the mid-project stakeholder forum and the final conference.	KPI on track with: 2 conferences organised attendance rate of 100+ and 690+ (online) All stakeholder groups represented.	A final conference will be organised and a series of events, targeting and dedicated to specific stakeholder groups
Non-scientific publications	EOSC portal magazine and other publications	1 news piece every quarter from M6 (in total)	KPI achieved with: 19 publications in external channels	Continue publications on external channels

6.9 Timeline for the next 6 months

The activities described in the preceding text are visually depicted in the March 2021 to September 2021 timeline below.

FIGURE 29: TIMELINE FOR ONBOARDING END USER COMMUNITIES ACTIVITIES IN M27-M32

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Annex I – SSHOC organised and co-organised engagement events until Dec 2020

Conference	Type event	Title	Date	No. Attendees	Target Stakeholder	Link
SSHOC workshop, Crete, Greece	workshop	Developing the SSHOC Reference Ontology	21-22/05/2019	41	Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-wp4-workshop-developing-sshoc-reference-ontology
LIBER 2019, Dublin, Ireland	workshop	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud: What's In It For Research Libraries?	26/06/2019	60	Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/liber-annual-event-workshop-social-sciences-humanities-open-cloud-what-s-it-research-libraries
DH 2019 Utrecht, Netherlands	workshop	The Case Of Interview Data – A multidisciplinary approach to the use of technology in research using interview methods	09/07/19	21	Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/digital-humanities-2019-workshop-case-interview-data
CLARIN annual conference in Leipzig , Germany	workshop	SSHOC Workshop: Using Corpora for Implementing Validation. Workflows that combine quantity and quality	30/09/2019	4	Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-workshop-using-corpora-implementing-validation-workflows-combine-quantity-and-quality
RDA Plenary 14, Helsinki, Finland	workshop	EOSC services, collaborations, and RDA	21/10/2019	43	Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/eosc-services-collaborations-and-rda
FAIR Research Data Management in SSH: a CO-OPERAS IN & SSHOC Workshop	Workshop	FAIR Research Data Management in SSH: a CO-OPERAS IN & SSHOC Workshop	30/01/2020	28	German speaking Ph.D Students, early career and senior scholars in the SSH	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/fair-research-data-management-ssh-co-operas-sshoc-workshop

Conference	Type event	Title	Date	No. Attendees	Target Stakeholder	Link
TEI training tutorial	workshop	TEI and Context: the TEITOK environment	20/2/2020	40	Scientific Community	https://lindat.cz/sites/default/files/lindat-tut-feb.pdf
SSHOC Webinar: CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data (online)	tutorial	CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data	03/03/20	attendees: 101 recordings seen 213 times	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/hands-on-tutorial-transcribing-interview-data#overlay-context=
SSHOC at HERItage conference 2020: The role of cultural heritage in socio-economic development and preservation of democratic values	parallel session	The Role of Cultural Heritage in Socio-Economic Development and Preservation of Democratic Values - HERItage	11-13/03/2020	cancelled due to COVID-19	SSH Researchers, EC and Croatian Policy Makers, EC and Croatian funders	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-heritage-conference-2020-role-cultural-heritage-socio-economic-development-and-preservation#overlay-context=
SSHOC training session during the COST Action meeting and 2nd Annual Policy Dialogue Conference, Brussels, Belgium	training session	Caring for Sharing: Data Management and FAIRness of Migration Data	9-10/03/20	33	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-training-session-cost-action-meeting#overlay-context=
SSHOC Webinar - Discussion meeting about requirements of CESSDA Service Providers for a Dataverse repository (online)	webinar	Discussion meeting about requirements of CESSDA Service Providers for a Dataverse repository	18/03/20	attendees 50, recordings seen 146 times	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-cessda-service-providers-dataverse#overlay-context=
SSHOC Training Community Kick-Off Call (online)	Kick-Off Call	SSHOC Training Community kick-off call	19/03/20	26	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-training-community-kick-call#overlay-context=
SSHOC Workshop - Linking Social Survey and Linguistic	workshop	Linking Social Survey and Linguistic Infrastructures through	24/03/2020	Postponed due to COVID-19	SSH research community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-workshop-linking-social-survey-

Conference	Type event	Title	Date	No. Attendees	Target Stakeholder	Link
Infrastructures through EOSC		EOSC				linguistic-infrastructures-eosc#overlay-context=
Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage	webinar	Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage	02/04/20	attendees 65, recordings seen 100 times	Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/use-and-re-use-scientific-data-archaeology-and-heritage
3rd SSHOC WEBINAR “Quanlify with ease: Combining quantitative and qualitative corpus analysis” (online)	webinar	Quanlify with Ease: Combining quantitative and qualitative corpus analysis	16/04/20	attendees 75, recordings seen 88 times	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/3rd-sshoc-webinar-quanlify-combining-quantitative-qualitative-corpus-analysis#overlay-context=
SSHOC WEBINAR: How to improve the quality of your repository? SSHOC and certification of repositories (online)	webinar	How to improve the quality of your repository? SSHOC and certification of repositories	23/04/20	attendees 54, recordings seen 98 times	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-repositories-quality-certification#overlay-context=
SSHOC OH-Portal Questions & Answers Session 1, 2, 3 and 4	Q&A sessions	OH-Portal: Questions & Answers Sessions	28/04/20, 05/05/2020, 12/05/2020, 19/05/2020	attendees of all 4 sessions: 0	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-oh-portal-questions-answers-session-1#overlay-context=
LR4SSHOC: LREC2020 workshop about Language Resources for the SSH Cloud	workshop	Workshop about Language Resources for the SSH Cloud (LR4SSHOC)	Planned 11/05/20 (postponed due to Covid-19)	Postponed due to COVID-19	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-repositories-quality-certification#overlay-context=
6th SSHOC webinar: Tools and	webinar	Tools and Resources for FAIR	18/05/20	attendees 136,	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-

Conference	Type event	Title	Date	No. Attendees	Target Stakeholder	Link
Resources for FAIR Data (online)		Data		recordings seen 153 times		webinar-emm-survey-data-fair#overlay-context=
Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Toolkit	workshop	Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Toolkit	02/06/2020	17	SSHOC Training Community members	
LIBER 2020 (online)	workshop	SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians	23/06/20	attendees 51	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-train-trainer-bootcamp-librarians#overlay-context=
ICTeSSH workshop - Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace	workshop	Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace	30/06/20	Attendees 246, recordings viewed 50 times	SSH research Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/agile-development-ssh-open-marketplace-user-workshop
SSH Open Marketplace - DARIAH consultation	webinar	SSH Open Marketplace - DARIAH consultation	03/07/2020	Attendees 25, recordings viewed 69 times	SSH research Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/ssh-open-marketplace-public-consultation-dariah-community
DH2020	workshop	Twin Talks 3 understanding and Facilitating collaboration in DH	23/07/2020	Attendees 64, recordings viewed 86 times	SSH research Community	https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/twintalksdh2020 https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/twin-talks-3_intro.pdf https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6Dcerw7a5TA&feature=youtu.be
SSHOC Online Information Sessions 1	workshop	SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - First session: Wikibase	03/09/2020	Attendees 41, Recordings were viewed 25 times	SSH Research Community	https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/sshoc-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms
SSHOC Online Information Sessions 2	workshop	SSHOC Online Information Sessions 2	14/09/2020	Attendees 61, Recordings were	SSH Research Community	https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/sshoc-sessions-open-source-

Conference	Type event	Title	Date	No. Attendees	Target Stakeholder	Link
				viewed 45 times		vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms
SSHOC Webinar – Discussion meeting about requirements of DARIAH community for a Dataverse repository	webinar	SSHOC Webinar – Discussion meeting about requirements of DARIAH community for a Dataverse repository	28/09/2020	Attendees 52, recordings viewed 36 times	SSH Research Community	https://www.dariah.eu/2020/09/01/sshoc-webinar-discussion-meeting-about-requirements-of-dariah-community-for-a-dataverse-repository/
SSHOC Online Information Session 3	workshop	SSHOC Online Information Session 3	30/09/2020	Attendees 57 , recordings viewed 23 times	SSH Research Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms-third
2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop	workshop	Hosting a Session Break out: Cross-fertilisation between thematic and horizontal projects	07/10/2020	10 invited attendees	ESFRI cluster projects & EOSC ecosystem	https://drive.google.com/file/d/14ansJbRBPEX676WwoWln6n8xgeg-hn2a/view?usp=sharing
Proposal discussion/validation with the ESFRI cluster projects	workshop	Workshop on Metadata catalogues integration for Interdisciplinary Research /II	09/10/2020	20 invited attendees	ESFRI cluster projects	https://bit.ly/MDCWS
SSHOC webinar	webinar	SSHOC Webinar: Sharing Datasets of Pathological Speech	14/10/2020	Attendees 74, recordings viewed 31 times	SSH Research Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-sharing-datasets-pathological-speech
DARIAH Annual Event	presentation	Building trustworthy repositories: Introduction to CoreTrustSeal certification workshop during DARIAH AE	14/10/2020	Attendees 20, recordings were viewed 58 times	SSH Research Community	https://dariah-ae-2020.sciencesconf.org/309393
Showcase and conduct a live demo of the EMM Survey	webinar	Showcase and conduct a live demo of the EMM Survey Registry	26/10/2020	Attendees 120, recordings were	SSH Research Community	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UFRj6Lz0v_w

Conference	Type event	Title	Date	No. Attendees	Target Stakeholder	Link
Registry				viewed 98 times		https://zenodo.org/record/4134061#.X7aPhRNKhZ0
SSHOC Virtual Workshop-consideration for the vocabulary platform	workshop	SSHOC Virtual Workshop-consideration for the vocabulary platform	06/11/2020	Attendees 60, recordings viewed 221 times	SSH Research Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-considerations-vocabulary-platforms
Joint EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC 4 day conference with 29 sessions organised	Conference & Virtual EOSC Expo	Realising EOSC. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences and humanities and beyond	16-19/11/2020	690+ Participants, From 45 Countries, including from 20 countries outside the EU 33 booths from EOSC projects, visited over 3780 times, 880 video views, 1520 document views	Universities & Research Institutes, Researchers, Research Funders, Research and e-Infrastructures, EOSC thematic clusters, Policy Makers, Citizen Scientists, Research Libraries & Archives, Private Sector and Industry	https://sshopencloud.eu/realising-european-open-science-cloud
Putting Data Protection into Practice – GDPR and the DARIAH ELDAH Consent Form Wizard	SSHOC webinar	Putting Data Protection into Practice – GDPR and the DARIAH ELDAH Consent Form Wizard	13.10.2020	41 attendees, recordings viewed 63 times	SSH Research Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/putting-data-protection-practice-gdpr-and-dariah-eldah-consent-form-wizard-0
Introducing the newly launched Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Registry	SSHOC webinar	Introducing the newly launched Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Registry	26.10.2020	107 attendees, recordings viewed 104 times	SSH Research Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-introducing-newly-launched-ethnic-and-migrant-minorities-emm-survey-registry
SSHOC-DARIAH RDM Train-The-Trainer Bootcamp	workshop	SSHOC-DARIAH RDM Train-The-Trainer Bootcamp	08/02/2021 and 11/02/2021	90	SSH Trainers	

Annex II - SSHOC raising awareness at third-party events until Dec 2020

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
Society for Historical Archaeology, USA	presentation	Roundtable presentation in workshop on Big Data synthesis	10/01/2019	20	Scientific Community	https://conference.timemachine.eu
Esfri Ris and EOSC Workshop, London	Workshop presentation		30/01/2019	250	RIs	https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-ris-eosc-workshop-speakers-ron-dekker
Eurise Workshop	session participation		13/03/2019		RI's	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/eurise-workshop-software-sustainability-within-research-infrastructures
4th International ESS Conference	Conference participation		15-17/04/2019		Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/4th-international-ess-conference-turbulent-times-europe-instability-insecurity-and-inequality
CSDI (Comparative studies and implementation workshop), Warsaw	Participation to a Workshop	Designing a Sample Management System for use in a cross-national on-line web panel: initial thinking and ideas	18-20/03/2019	75	Scientific Community	https://csdiworkshop.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Designing-a-Sample-Management-System-for-use-in-a-cross-national-on-line-web-panel.pdf
RDA Plenary 13, Philadelphia, US	Presentation	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud	04/04/2019	75	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3610082#.XiGFjP5KiCg

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
EOSC hub week 2019	session participation	EOSC for Social Sciences and Humanities	10-12/04/2019	100	EOSC ecosystem	https://sshopencloud.eu/eosc-hub-week
	poster presentation	Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities part of the EOSC	10-12/04/2019	100	EOSC ecosystem	https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/eosc-hub-week-2019/posters# and https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3626960
4th International ESS Conference	Conference participation		15-17/04/2019		Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/4th-international-ess-conference-turbulent-times-europe-instability-insecurity-and-inequality
Computer Applications in Archaeology Annual Conference, Krakow, Poland	presentation	Digital Infrastructures for Archaeology: Past, Present and Future directions	24/04/2019	50	Scientific Community	https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/resources/images/presentations/2019/PDFa/jdr_introduction_CAA_ARIADNEplus_2019.pdf
ArchAIDE final conference, Pisa, Italy	presentation	Open Data and ARCHAIDE	13-15/05/2019	70	Scientific Community	https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/resources/images/presentations/2019/PDFa/jdr_Open_Data_and_ArchAIDE.pdf
DARIAH 2019, Warsaw, Poland	presentation		13-17/05/2019	100	Scientific Community	https://dariah-ae-2019.sciencesconf.org/261285

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
C25XVIII International Scientific and Practical conference "BUILDING OF INFORMATION SOCIETY: RESOURCES AND TECHNOLOGIES, Kyiv, Ukraine	presentation	Building an electronic repository and archives in the European Open Science Cloud Tykhonov, Vyacheslav	21/05/2019		Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3598601#.XiBWL1x85g
Dataverse Community meeting at Harvard University, USA.	presentation	pyDataverse	20-21/06/2019		Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3265128
	presentation	Dataverse in the European Open Science Cloud Tykhonov, Vyacheslav; Conzett, Philipp; Wittenberg, Marion.SSHOC project presented during Dataverse Community meeting at Harvard University, USA.	20-21/06/2019	110	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3598611#.XiA9GS1x-L4
IIIF Conference 2019, Goettingen, Germany	participation to conference		24-28/06/2019	300	Scientific Community	https://iiif.io/event/2019/goettingen/
LIBER 2019, Dublin, Ireland	poster presentation	Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities part of the European Open Science Cloud	26-28/06/2019	450	Libraries & Archives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3633016
DH2019 Conference	SSHOC booth		9-12/07/2019		Scientific Community	https://dh2019.adho.org

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
Synergies for Europe's Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences: Showcasing the SERISS project, Zagreb, Croatia	Presentation + video	Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities part of the EOSC	15-19/07/2019	100	RIs	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/4th-international-ess-conference-turbulent-times-europe-instability-insecurity-and-inequality
"Culture & Technology" European Summer University in Digital Humanities	Lecture	Language as social and cultural data	02/08/2019		Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/culture-technology-european-summer-university-digital-humanities
European Archaeology Conference, Bern, Switzerland	presentation	Making Archaeological Data FAIR	05/09/2019	30	Scientific Community	https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/resources/images/presentations/2019/PDFa/jdr_EAA_2019.pdf
COST Action CA16111 (ETHMIGSURVEYDATA) meeting, Rome, Italy	Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)	International Ethnic and Immigrant Minorities Survey Data Network (ETHMIGSURVEYDATA)	8-9/09/2019	50	Scientific Community	https://ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/executive-wg-meeting-and-mc-meeting/
DG CNECT & RTD meeting	Workshop presentation	Building EOSC through H2020 projects	9-10/09/2019		EC and EOSC ecosystem	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/building-eosc-through-h2020-projects
CLARIN 2019, Leipzig, Germany	poster presentation	Realising the Social Sciences and Humanities for the European Open Science Cloud	30/09/2019 - 02/10/2019		Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3633039

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
Time Machine conference'19, Dresden, Germany	presentation	Running Dataverse repository in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Tykhonov, Vyacheslav	12/10/2019	500	Scientific Community	
DDI workshop at GESIS	Participation to a Workshop		17/10/2019		Scientific Community	
OS FAIR 2019, Porto, Portugal	poster presentation	Social Sciences and Humanities Community Building: Training - Open Science FAIR	16-18/10/2019		Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3633059
	presentation	Open Science Training for Library Staff & Researchers	16-18/10/2019	60	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3427305#.XianCf5KiCg
RDA P14 - EOSC at RDA, Helsinki, Finland	Participation to a Workshop	The International Research Community Contributing to the EOSC	21-25/10/2019	250	EOSC ecosystem	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/international-research-data-community-contributing-eosc
	presentation	Building Dataverse Communities that follow RDA Best Practices for Data Sharing and Management. Part of Presentation Presentation at RDA 2019 in Helsinki, Finland by Vyacheslav Tykhonov	21-25/10/2019		Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3598658#.Xia71y1x-L4
	Booth	EOSC KIOSK	21-25/10/2019	400	Scientific Community	

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
CESSDA's Mentorship Programme Promotes Knowledge Exchange between European Data Archives	Participation to a Workshop		5-6/11/2019		Libraries & Archives	https://www.CESSDA.eu/News-Events/News/CESSDA/CESSDA-s-Mentorship-Programme-Promotes-Knowledge-Exchange-between-European-Data-Archives
DESIR Final Event, Zagreb, Croatia	participation to conference		5-6/11/2019	60	Scientific Community	https://www.dariah.eu/2019/10/30/desir-final-event-and-dariah-general-assembly-in-november/
Open Access Ambassadors Conference	Presentation at Conference		10-11/12/2019		Scientific Community	https://oambassadors.mpdl.mpg.de/
CLARIAH-DE 1st General Assembly, Tübingen, Germany	participation to conference		14-15/11/2019	50	Scientific Community	https://hdl.handle.net/10037/15901
SHAREcare, Amsterdam, The Netherlands http://sharecare.nu/presentations-amsterdam/	presentation		22/11/2019	50	Scientific Community	https://www.slideshare.net/ShareCareX/07-reusable-padfield
Europeana 2019	Workshop presentation	New perspectives for Digital Cultural Heritage	27/11/2019		Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/europeana-2019-eosc-digital-cultural-heritage
EOSC symposium 2019	Panel discussion	Social & Cultural Data – taking the Users' Perspective	27-29/11/2019	200	EOSC ecosystem	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/eosc-symposium-2019

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
	poster presentation	A marketplace for the Social Sciences and Humanities	27-29/11/2019	200	EOSC ecosystem	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3550957
	Booth	EOSC KIOSK	27-29/11/2019	200	EOSC ecosystem	
EDDI conference	presentation	Enrichment of DDI support in the Dataverse data repository. Tykhonov, Slava; Wittenberg, Marion	12/01/2019		Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/3600093#.XiAbS1x-L4
TRIPLE kick-off meeting	Presentation at Conference		04/12/2019		EOSC ecosystem	https://operas.hypotheses.org/3007
Roundtable presentation in workshop on Big Data synthesis, Society for Historical Archaeology, USA	Participation to a Workshop		10/1/20	20	Scientific Community	
"International migration data: advances and challenges" Workshop, Bologna, IT	Participation to a Workshop,	"The Ethnic and Migrant Minorities Survey Metadata Registry: a new tool for understanding data on migration", Session 1. Advances in migration data usage and collection. Presentation by Laura Morales (Lead of T9.2) of the EMM Survey Registry	13/02/20	25	Scientific Community	https://eventi.unibo.it/workshopcassini-bologna-2020

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
CLOSER Conference 2020, Preparing for the future II: international approaches to challenges facing the longitudinal population studies, Woburn House, London (UK)	Presentation of Mari Kleemola	Challenges and successes of CESSDA ERIC	16/01/20		Scientific Community	https://www.closer.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/Data-discoverability-and-issues-of-interoperability-C3-Kleemola-Mari.pdf
EOSC French days	Participation to a Workshop	SSHOC presentation at EOSC French days	22/1/20	100	Scientific Community	
Dataverse Workshop	European Use Cases Round table discussion	SSHOC Dataverse	24/01/2020		Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/european-dataverse-workshop-2020
NCCR - On the Move Public Lectures Series, Neuchâtel, CH	Participation to a Workshop, Presentation by Laura Morales (Lead of T9.2) of the EMM Survey Registry,	Mapping Contemporary Patterns of Mobility, Migration and Integration: What Survey Data Can We Use?	20/2/20	15	Scientific Community	https://nccr-onthemove.ch/events/mapping-contemporary-patterns-of-mobility-migration-and-integration-what-survey-data-can-we-use/
CSDI2020	Workshop	2020 International Workshop on Comparative Survey Design and Implementation Program	11-13/3/20	cancelled	-	https://csdiworkshop.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/2020-CSDI-Program-2_20.pdf
EOSC-hub Week 2020 goes virtual	Poster presentation	EOSC-hub Week 2020	18-20/05/20	800	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/eosc-hub-week-2020-goes-virtual#overlay-context=

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
RDA global adoption week 2020	presentations in 2 sessions	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) adoption story of CoreTrustSeal across European SSH repositories	17/06/2020	100	Scientific Community	https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-global-adoption-week-15-19-june-2020
17th IMISCOE Annual Conference	Via a panel session, present working paper that analyses survey-level metadata from the EMM Survey Registry	EMM survey registry	01/07/2020	20	Scientific Community	https://www.imiscoe.org/events/imiscoe-events/1027-17th-imiscoe-annual-conference
	Via a roundtable, present EMM Survey Registry (beta version) to potential users	EMM survey registry (beta version)	02/07/2020	30	Scientific Community	https://www.imiscoe.org/events/imiscoe-events/1027-17th-imiscoe-annual-conference
Workshop on Metadata catalogues integration for Interdisciplinary Research	Presentation	Workshop on Metadata catalogues integration for Interdisciplinary Research	11/09/2020	60	Scientific Community	https://bit.ly/MDCWS
Open Access Tage 2020	Presentation	Presentation of SSH Open Marketplace at the Open-Access-Tage 2020	16/09/2020	30	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/4009121
EOSC & SRIA, Clusters, SSHOC Tier-1 Meeting, virtual, 16.09.2020	Presentation	EOSC & SRIA, Clusters, SSHOC Tier-1 Meeting, virtual, 16.09.2020	16/09/2020	10	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1nyLwjrutDljTgeAMxsh0eKi3Bs-OLsId/view?usp=sharing

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
RESILIENCE Community Meeting	Presentation	Presentation of SSHOC Project at RESILIENCE community meeting	18/09/2020	6	Scientific Community	general SSHOC presentation provided by WP2
CLARIN Annual Conference 2020	Pitch	mention of SSHOC project at CLARIN Annual Conference 2020	06/10/2020		Scientific Community	https://www.clarin.eu/blog/clarin2020-visual-wrap-day-2 https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/clarin2020_stateoftheinfrastructure_dejong.pdf
	Booth	Bazaar booth at the CLARIN Annual Conference			Scientific Community	https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-bazaar-2020#CLARIN%20in%20SSHOC
2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop		presentation at 2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop	06/10/2020	250	Scientific Community	https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/DeJong_Session-4_ESFRI-EOSC_07.10.20.pdf
TRIPLE project Consortium meeting	Participation to an Event	Presentation of SSHOC Services at the TRIPLE project Consortium meeting	13/10/2020	24	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1X9lgdjnc-dIUO6TfPQQ2wAevj7zrAPx/view?usp=sharing
General Assembly EURHISFIRM	Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)	SSHOC at EURHISFIRM, General Assembly EURHISFIRM, virtual, 16.10.2020	16/10/2020	50	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qgr5X_LW5hzCQ_nv8An52wJlm7GFdDb/view?usp=sharing

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
Presentation was conducted as part of ETHMIGSURVEYDATA's Management Committee and Work Groups meeting	Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)	Provide updates on the development of the EMM Survey Registry and the QDB pilots (to test the feasibility of including EMM surveys in the CESDDA-led EQB), which are being jointly developed by SSHOC (T9.2) and ETHMIGSURVEYDATA	29/10/2020	50	Scientific Community	
21st ESS ERIC Core Scientific Team Meeting	Participation to an Event	21st ESS ERIC Core Scientific Team Meeting	29/10/2020	20	Scientific Community	
ICMI2020	Workshop presentations	Speech, Voice, Text, and Meaning about Oral History and Technology	29/10/2020	18	Scientific Community	http://icmi.acm.org/2020/index.php?id=workshops#workshop10
OPERAS Conference	Presentation	Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities, OPERAS conference, virtual, 04.11.2020	04/11/2020	80	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qgr5X_LW5hzCQ_nv8An52wjl7GFdDb/view?usp=sharing
BigSurv20 conference	Presentation	Improving SHARE translation verification	06/11/2020	40	Scientific Community & Industry	https://www.bigsurv20.org/glance; https://www.bigsurv20.org/conf20/uploads/138/197/SSHOC_ATV_Pettinicchi.pdf
	Presentation	Developing a tool suite for managing large scale cross-national web surveys within the framework	20/11/2020		Scientific Community	https://www.bigsurv20.org/conf20/program/?sess=33#136

Conference	Activity	Title	Date	No. Stakeholders targeted	Target Stakeholder	Link
		of the European Open Science Cloud - Demonstrate the "Web panel sample management service" first use case with CRONOS2	21/11/2020		Scientific Community	https://www.bigsurv20.org/conf20/program/?sess=33#137
15th ESS ERIC National Coordinators Forum	Participation	15th ESS ERIC National Coordinators Forum	11/11/2020	50	Scientific Community	
DARIAH Annual Event	Presentation	DARIAH Public Demonstration of the SSH Open Marketplace	13/11/2020		Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4290536
Meeting with EC DG RTD	Presentation	Presentation of SSHOC Project at meeting with EC DG RTD	01/12/2020	5	Policy Makers	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mBdFM/Dk2e0OQ4MhneJRUGalvubuHahiO/view?usp=sharing
DDI2020	Presentation	As part of session 6, give a presentation (Reusing and sharing metadata: A case study of quantitative survey research on the integration of ethnic and migrant minorities (EMMs) across Europe) about how the EMM Survey Registry promotes the re-use and sharing of EMM surveys via metadata	02/12/2020	40	Scientific Community	https://eddi20.sciencesconf.org/program; http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4305692; https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YtB14nQn79Q&list=PLo7wmlY6eAWlwMy8uoGCVyYCc4uQSRrZh&index=2&t=30s
French Data SHS 2020	Presentation	Present the EMM Survey Registry and the French EMM surveys that will be included in the registry	10/12/2020		Scientific Community	http://migrinter.labo.univ-poitiers.fr/semaine-data-shs/

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French Data SHS 2020	Presentation	Present the EMM Survey Registry and the French EMM surveys that will be included in the registry	11/12/2020		Scientific Community	https://progedo.hypotheses.org/1184
ESFRI Strategic Working Group and EEASH Community	Presentation	Presentation of SSHOC Project at a meeting with ESFRI Strategic Working Group and EEASH Community	18/12/2020	4	Research Infrastructures	closed meeting